

Kinetics and mechanism of iridium(III) catalysed oxidation of tellurium(IV) by cerium(IV) in sulfuric acid medium

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The kinetics and mechanism of iridium(III) catalysed oxidation of tellurium(IV) by cerium(IV) have been studied in sulfuric acid medium. The reaction is first order in $[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]$ as well as in $[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]$ and fractional order (0.23) in $[\text{Te}^{\text{IV}}]$. Increase in $[\text{H}_3\text{O}^+]$ accelerates the rate while that in ionic strength or $[\text{HSO}_4^-]$ retards. Ce^{III} , one of the products, inhibits while the other, Te^{VI} , has negligible effect on the rate. The reaction is supposed to proceed via the formation of a complex between Te^{IV} and Ir^{III} which in turn reacts with active Ce^{IV} species in a reversible step. A rate law, consistent with the observed kinetic data, has been derived basing on the proposed mechanism.

While attempting to develop newer oxidimetric methods for the determination of tellurium, it was noticed that the oxidation of tellurium(IV) by cerium(IV) is much slower than that by chromium(VI). Since this is contrary to what is normally expected from the standard redox potentials of the systems concerned, detailed kinetic studies were conducted and the behaviour was explained proposing suitable mechanisms^{1,2}. In continuation of the studies on the mechanism of oxidation of tellurium(IV) by cerium(IV) in sulfuric acid medium, catalysis by osmium(VIII) and ruthenium(III) was also investigated³. As iridium(III) is being increasingly utilised as yet another newer transition metal catalyst in many redox reactions in solution, we attempted its catalysis on the title reaction and the results, which are entirely different from those obtained with osmium(VIII) or ruthenium(III) as catalyst, are presented in this communication.

Results and Discussion

Stoichiometry : In one set of experiments, known amounts of Te^{IV} were mixed with excess of a standard Ce^{IV} solution in presence of Ir^{III} as catalyst in 1.0 mol dm^{-3} sulfuric acid and after 24 h the residual $[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]$ in each case was determined with standard Fe^{II} solution using ferroin as indicator. In another set of experiments, under similar conditions, known amounts of Ce^{IV} were mixed with excess of standard Te^{IV} solution and the residual Te^{IV} , after completion of the reaction, was estimated using standard Cr^{VI} solution⁴. The stoichiometry in either of the cases, was found to correspond to

Preliminary experiments showed that the uncatalysed reaction proceeds at negligible rate compared to the catalysed

reaction under the experimental conditions employed in this study and hence the results pertain to the catalysed reaction only. The course of the reaction was followed under the conditions, $[\text{Te}^{\text{IV}}] \gg [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] \gg [\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]$. The plots of log (absorbance) versus time were found to be straight-lines even beyond 75% completion of the reaction indicating that the reaction is first order in cerium(IV) under the conditions. The pseudo-first order rate constant (k') calculated from such plots were found to be reproducible within $\pm 3\%$ for identical runs.

Effect of products on rate : In order to study the effect of products, viz. Ce^{III} and Te^{VI} on the rate of the reaction, kinetic runs were carried out at varying initial concentrations of Ce^{III} or Te^{VI} , keeping all other factors constant and the data obtained are shown in Table 1. The data show that initial presence of Ce^{III} in the medium has a retarding effect on the reaction rate while that of Te^{VI} has negligible effect. So as to minimise the effect of $[\text{Ce}^{\text{III}}]$, produced during the course of the reaction, all subsequent kinetic runs were carried out keeping an excess initial $[\text{Ce}^{\text{III}}]$.

Dependence on ionic strength : The effect of ionic strength (μ) on the rate of the reaction was studied by varying the concentration of LiClO_4 in the medium, keeping all other conditions constant and the results (Table 1) reveal that increase in μ causes a slight decrease in the rate.

Dependence on $[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]$: The fact that a plot of log (absorbance) versus time was a straight-line ($r = 0.99$) up to at least 75% completion of the reaction, under the conditions $[\text{Te}^{\text{IV}}]_{\text{T}} \gg [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]_{\text{T}}$, where $[\]_{\text{T}}$ refers to the total concentration of the reactant, shows that the order with respect to $[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]$ is unity. Further similar straight lines showing first order dependence on $[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]_{\text{T}}$ were also obtained when different initial concentrations of Ce^{IV} were employed, while

keeping the other factors constant (Fig. 1). However, the numerical values of the pseudo-first order rate constant (k') instead of remaining constant, were found to decrease with increase in initial $[Ce^{IV}]$. Even when the kinetics were followed in the initial absence of $[Ce^{III}]$ by initial rate method, the rate constant was found to decrease with increase in initial $[Ce^{IV}]$.

Dependence on $[Te^{IV}]$: To know the dependence of rate on $[Te^{IV}]$, kinetic runs were carried out at different initial $[Te^{IV}]$ keeping the remaining conditions constant. A plot of $1/k'$ versus $1/[Te^{IV}]_T$ was also found to be a straight line ($r = 0.99$) with positive slope ($m = 8.7 \pm 0.3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ s}$) and intercept ($c = 2.340 \times 10^3 \pm 1.9 \text{ s}$) on y-axis, indicating complex formation of one of the active species with Te^{IV} . Similar results were also obtained when the same variation studies were conducted at 30, 40 and 45°.

Dependence on $[Ir^{III}]_T$: To determine the order with respect to Ir^{III} , k' was determined at varying initial $[Ir^{III}]$ and maintaining the other factors constant. When the pseudo-first order rate constants obtained in these runs were plotted against the corresponding $[Ir^{III}]_T$, a straight-line ($r = 0.99$) with a positive slope and passing through the origin was obtained indicating the order with respect to $[Ir^{III}]_T$ to be unity and the contribution from $[Ir^{III}]$ independent path to the rate to be negligible.

Dependence on $[H^+]$: In order to study the effect of $[H^+]$ on the rate, kinetic runs were carried out using $HClO_4$ to vary the $[H^+]$ and $LiClO_4$ to maintain constant ionic strength and keeping the remaining conditions constant. The pseudo-first order rate constants obtained were found to increase with increase in $[H^+]$ (Table 1).

Fig. 1. Order with respect to $[Ce^{IV}]_T$; $[Te^{IV}]_T = 1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[Ce^{III}]_0 = 1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[Ir^{III}]_T = 1.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[H_2SO_4] = 0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\mu = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ ($LiClO_4$), temp. = 35°.

Table 1. Effect of $[Ce^{III}]$, $[Te^{VI}]$, $[HSO_4^-]$, $[H^+]$ and μ on pseudo-first order rate constant, k'

$10^3 [Ce^{III}]_T = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $10^2 [Te^{VI}]_T = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $10^5 [Ir^{III}]_T = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$	$10^3 [Ce^{III}]_0$	$10^3 [Te^{VI}]_0$	$[HSO_4^-]_e$	$[H^+]_e$	$[\mu]$	$10^4 k'$
mol dm ⁻³	mol dm ⁻³	mol dm ⁻³	mol dm ⁻³	mol dm ⁻³	mol dm ⁻³	s ⁻¹
-	-	0.49	0.51	1.0	12.5	
1.0	-	0.49	0.51	1.0	7.46	
3.0	-	0.49	0.51	1.0	5.65	
5.0	-	0.49	0.51	1.0	4.54	
7.5	-	0.49	0.51	1.0	4.10	
-	2.5	0.49	0.51	1.0	12.5	
-	5.0	0.49	0.51	1.0	12.4	
-	10.0	0.49	0.51	1.0	12.3	
-	12.5	0.49	0.51	1.0	12.6	
-	15.0	0.49	0.51	1.0	12.4	
10.0	-	0.74	0.51	2.0	2.32	
10.0	-	0.98	0.52	2.0	1.86	
10.0	-	1.23	0.52	2.0	1.61	
10.0	-	1.72	0.53	2.0	1.26	
10.0	-	1.96	0.54	2.0	1.14	
10.0	-	0.99	1.00	4.0	1.78	
10.0	-	0.99	1.50	4.0	2.37	
10.0	-	0.99	2.00	4.0	2.86	
10.0	-	0.99	3.00	4.0	3.76	
10.0	-	0.99	4.00	4.0	4.53	
10.0	-	0.49	0.51	0.5	4.96	
10.0	-	0.49	0.51	0.8	4.43	
10.0	-	0.49	0.51	1.0	4.00	
10.0	-	0.49	0.51	1.5	3.67	
10.0	-	0.49	0.51	2.0	2.97	

Dependence on $[HSO_4^-]$: The effect of $[HSO_4^-]$ on the rate of the reaction was studied by varying $[HSO_4^-]_e$ using $NaHSO_4$ as a source of HSO_4^- , keeping $[H^+]_e$ almost constant and the other factors also constant and the results (Table 1) reveal that increase in $[HSO_4^-]_e$ causes a decrease in k' .

From the earlier reports² it may be presumed that Te^{IV} exists as $TeO(OH)^+$ or $Te(OH)_3^+$ under the experimental conditions employed in the present study. Depending upon the concentrations of H^+ , HSO_4^- and H_2SO_4 , Ce^{IV} was reported^{5,6} to be present in different forms such as Ce^{4+} , $Ce(SO_4)^{2+}$, $Ce(SO_4)_2$, $Ce(SO_4)_2^{2-}$, $HCe(SO_4)_3^-$, $H_2Ce(SO_4)_4^{3-}$, $H_2Ce(SO_4)_4^{2-}$, $H_3Ce(SO_4)_4^-$ and $H_4Ce(SO_4)_4$ in sulfuric acid media. Basing on the effect shown by $[H^+]$ and $[HSO_4^-]$ on the rate of reaction one or other of these species were treated to be the reactive species of Ce^{IV} in the oxidation of different substrates by cerium(IV). Some of the equilibria⁵ leading to the formation of sulfato complexes of Ce^{IV} include,

The most relevant equilibria among the above, under the conditions employed in the present work, appear to be (A) and (B) with $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2$ and $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_3^{2-}$ as the predominant species of Ce^{IV} . However, the numerical values of the above equilibrium constants obtained in turn depend upon that of the dissociation constant of HSO_4^- used⁷ in the calculation.

Even though Ir^{III} was used as a catalyst in the study of the kinetics and mechanism of some redox reactions in sulfuric acid media⁸ no information on the species of Ir^{III} is available from these reports. According to Livingstone⁹, $[\text{Ir}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+}$ is not known and apart from a few mono-aquachloro complexes, no solid complexes containing coordinated water have been isolated. On passing the yellow coloured Ir^{III} solution in $0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ H}_2\text{SO}_4$, obtained by repeated evaporation of iridium(III) chloride with concentrated sulfuric acid (to expel Cl^-), through Amberlite IRA 400 anion exchange resin in the nitrate form, the Ir^{III} was retained on the resin indicating Ir^{III} to be present in an anionic sulfato complex in the solution. The existence of yellow coloured alums⁹, $\text{M}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($\text{M} = \text{K}^+, \text{Rb}^+, \text{Cs}^+, \text{NH}_4^+, \text{H}^+$) lends support to this surmise. Moreover, Ir^{III} was also reported to form cationic, neutral and anionic complexes with a variety of ligands with a preference for soft ligands. Formation of an outer-sphere complex between the substrate and Ir^{III} was proposed (basing on kinetic evidence only) as a prelude to electron transfer from the complex to the oxidant in the rate-determining step in many of the Ir^{III} catalysed oxidations^{8,10}. However, we did not get any spectrophotometric evidence for the formation of either $\text{Te}^{\text{IV}}-\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}$, $\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}-\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}$ or $\text{Te}^{\text{IV}}-\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}$ complex under the conditions employed in the present work.

Mechanism : Keeping the various aspects in view as well as the kinetic evidence obtained for the formation of a tellurium(IV) complex in the present investigation, we propose the following mechanism for the Ir^{III} catalysed oxidation of Te^{IV} by Ce^{IV} , which invokes the complexation of Ir^{III} with Te^{IV} as an equilibrium step prior to the electron transfer to Ce^{IV} . The fact that Te^{IV} exists as $\text{TeO}(\text{OH})^+$ and the observation that Ir^{III} species bears a negative charge under the conditions employed in this study, also favour an association between Te^{IV} and Ir^{III} ,

where Ce^{4+} stands for the active species of cerium(IV) and C_2 is an intermediate composed of tellurium and iridium. The fact that $[\text{Ce}^{\text{III}}]$ inhibits while $[\text{Te}^{\text{VI}}]$ has no influence on the rate supports the case of step (2) as a reversible step. After applying steady state approximation to $[\text{C}_2]$, mass balance to $[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]$ and making certain reasonable approximations, the mechanism leads to the rate equation,

$$\frac{-d[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]}{dt} = \frac{2k_1k_3K_1[\text{Te}^{\text{IV}}]_{\text{T}}[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}}[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]^2}{(k_2[\text{Ce}^{\text{III}}] + k_3[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}])(1 + K_1[\text{Te}^{\text{IV}}]_{\text{T}})} \quad (4)$$

where the symbol $[\]_{\text{T}}$ denotes total concentration.

Expression (4) explains the fractional order in $[\text{Te}^{\text{IV}}]_{\text{T}}$, unit order in $[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}}$ and inhibition by $[\text{Ce}^{\text{III}}]$.

Assuming $k_2[\text{Ce}^{\text{III}}] \ll k_3[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]$, eq. (4) becomes

$$\frac{-d[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]}{dt} = \frac{2k_1K_1[\text{Te}^{\text{IV}}]_{\text{T}}[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}}[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]}{(1 + K_1[\text{Te}^{\text{IV}}]_{\text{T}})} \quad (5)$$

where $[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]$ represents the concentration of active species of cerium(IV).

Calculations based on the reported values⁵ of K , K' and K'' show that $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2$ and $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_3^{2-}$ are the only species of cerium(IV) present at significant concentration under the conditions employed in this work and hence basing mainly on equilibrium (A), the mass balance equation for $[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]$ is

$$[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]_{\text{T}} = [\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2]_{\text{e}} + [\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_3^{2-}]_{\text{e}} \quad (6)$$

where the symbols $[\]_{\text{T}}$ and $[\]_{\text{e}}$ denote the total and equilibrium concentrations, respectively. The effects of $[\text{H}^+]$ and $[\text{HSO}_4^-]$ on the rate of the present reaction clearly suggest that $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2$ is the reactive species. Therefore, from eqs. (A) and (6), it follows that

$$[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] = [\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2]_{\text{e}} = \frac{[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]_{\text{T}}[\text{H}^+]_{\text{e}}}{([\text{H}^+]_{\text{e}} + K[\text{HSO}_4^-]_{\text{e}})} \quad (7)$$

Substituting for $[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]$ from eq. (7), eq. (5) becomes

$$\frac{-d[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]}{dt} = \frac{2k_1K_1[\text{Te}^{\text{IV}}]_{\text{T}}[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}}[\text{H}^+]_{\text{e}}[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]_{\text{T}}}{(1 + K_1[\text{Te}^{\text{IV}}]_{\text{T}})([\text{H}^+]_{\text{e}} + K[\text{HSO}_4^-]_{\text{e}})} \quad (8)$$

Under the conditions $[H^+]_e, [HSO_4^-]_e \gg [Te^{IV}]_T \gg [Ce^{IV}]_T$, as the total concentration of the catalyst is also a constant, the pseudo-first order rate constant is given by

$$k' = \frac{2k_1K_1[Te^{IV}]_T[Ir^{III}]_T[H^+]_e}{(1 + K_1[Te^{IV}]_T)([H^+]_e + K[HSO_4^-]_e)} \quad (9)$$

If $[H^+]_e$ and $[HSO_4^-]_e$ are kept constant, eq. (9) becomes

$$k' = \frac{2ak_1K_1[Te^{IV}]_T[Ir^{III}]_T}{(1 + K_1[Te^{IV}]_T)} \quad (10)$$

where, $a = \frac{[H^+]_e}{([H^+]_e + K[HSO_4^-]_e)}$

which is equal to the fraction of $[Ce^{IV}]_T$ present as the active species. Taking reciprocals on both sides, eq. (10) becomes

$$\frac{1}{k'} = \frac{1}{2ak_1K_1[Ir^{III}]_T[Te^{IV}]_T} + \frac{1}{2ak_1[Ir^{III}]_T} \quad (11)$$

If the above treatment is correct, a plot of $1/k'$ versus $1/[Te^{IV}]_T$ (at constant $\mu, [H^+]_e, [HSO_4^-]_e, [Ir^{III}]_T$ and temperature) must be a straight-line with a positive slope and intercept on y-axis. This was observed to be the case not only at a particular temperature but also at different temperatures. Further, it should also be possible to calculate the values of ak_1 and K_1 , at each temperature from the corresponding slope and intercept of the respective straight-lines, which was found to be the case actually. Moreover, eq. (9) can also be represented as

$$k' = \frac{k[H^+]_e}{[H^+]_e + K[HSO_4^-]_e} \quad (12)$$

where, $k = \frac{2kK_1[Te^{IV}]_T[Ir^{III}]_T}{(1 + K_1[Te^{IV}]_T)}$

which may be treated as a constant under the conditions $[Te^{IV}]_T \gg [Ce^{IV}]_T$, as $[Ir^{III}]_T$ is also constant. Taking reciprocals on both sides, eq. (12) becomes

$$\frac{1}{k'} = \frac{1}{k} + \frac{K}{k} \frac{[HSO_4^-]_e}{[H^+]_e} \quad (13)$$

As per the above relation, a plot of $1/k'$ versus $1/[H^+]_e$, if the other factors are kept constant, must be a straight-line with a positive slope and intercept on y-axis which was found to be the case. Similarly, a plot of $1/k'$ versus $[HSO_4^-]_e / [H^+]_e$ must also be a straight-line with a positive slope and

intercept on y-axis, at constant $[Te^{IV}]_T, [Ir^{III}]_T, \mu$ and temperature. Further, from the ratio of slope to intercept of the line it should be possible to evaluate K . Fig. 2 confirms that these arguments are valid and the numerical value of K at 30, 35, 40 and 45° were determined from this graph. Incidentally, the figure also supports the surmise that $Ce(SO_4)_2$ is the reactive species of cerium(IV) in the present case; the relative equilibrium concentrations of HSO_4^- and H^+ were calculated basing on the reported¹¹ values of dissociation constant of HSO_4^- at the corresponding temperatures and the initial concentrations of H^+ and HSO_4^- employed.

Fig. 2. Plots of $1/k'$ versus $[HSO_4^-]_e/[H^+]_e$ at different temperatures; $[Ce^{IV}]_T = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[Ce^{III}]_0 = 1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[Te^{IV}]_T = 1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[Ir^{III}]_T = 1.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\mu = 2.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ ($LiClO_4$).

Using the K values obtained at different temperatures along with the known equilibrium concentrations of HSO_4^- and H^+ , a values were calculated and substituted in the factor ak_1 obtained (eq. 10) to get the corresponding k_1 value at the desired temperature (the same ionic strength was maintained in $[Te^{IV}]_T$ and $[HSO_4^-]_e/[H^+]_e$ variations studies). The numerical values of K_1, K and k_1 so calculated are shown in Table 2. The pseudo-first order rate constant values calcu-

Table 2. Numerical values of K_1, K and k_1 at different temperatures (from $[Te^{IV}]_T$ and $[HSO_4^-]_e/[H^+]_e$ variation studies at different temperatures)

$10^3 [Ce^{IV}]_T = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $10^2 [Ce^{III}]_0 = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $10^5 [Ir^{III}]_T = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\mu = 2.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ ($LiClO_4$)

Temp. °C	K_1 mol ⁻¹ dm ⁻³	K	k_1 mol ⁻¹ dm ³ s ⁻¹
30	265	1.44	32.3
35	269	1.60	54.2
40	283	1.62	85.2
45	297	1.65	132.0

lated by substituting the graphically determined values of K_1 , K and k_1 and the known concentrations of the various reactants in eq. (9) were found to be in very good agreement (Table 3) with the experimentally observed pseudo-first order rate constant [obtained from log (absorbance) versus

Table 3. A tally of observed and calculated values of pseudo-first order rate constant, k'

$10^3 [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]_{\text{T}} = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $10^2 [\text{Ce}^{\text{III}}]_0 = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $10^5 [\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}} = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\mu = 2.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (LiClO_4)

Temp. °C	$10^2 [\text{Te}^{\text{IV}}]_{\text{T}}$ mol dm ⁻³	$[\text{H}^+]_{\text{e}}$ mol dm ⁻³	$[\text{HSO}_4^-]_{\text{e}}$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^4 k', \text{ s}^{-1}$	
				Obs.	Calc.
30	1.00	0.54	1.96	7.22	7.57
30	1.50	0.51	0.49	2.16	2.16
30	2.00	0.51	0.49	2.31	2.28
35	1.00	0.51	0.49	3.10	3.12
35	1.50	0.51	0.49	3.41	3.42
35	0.80	0.51	0.49	2.92	2.92
40	1.00	0.53	1.47	2.24	2.28
40	1.20	0.51	0.49	5.13	5.15
40	1.50	0.51	0.49	5.40	5.39
45	1.00	0.52	1.23	4.08	4.05
45	1.50	0.51	0.49	8.31	8.34
45	0.80	0.51	0.49	7.16	7.19

time plots] giving further credibility to the proposed mechanism. It was observed that the second order rate constant (k_1) of step (2) in the proposed mechanism obeys Arrhenius temperature dependence ($r = 0.99$) and the values of E_a and ΔS_{308}^\ddagger for the forward reaction were found to be $75.6 \pm 2.8 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $+24.7 \pm 0.7 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$, respectively.

As the ionic strengths employed were very high for the Brönsted relation to be strictly applicable¹², the observed slight decrease in the rate with increase in ionic strength may be ignored.

As mentioned earlier, the pseudo-first order rate constant instead of remaining constant, decreases with increase in the initial $[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]$. Similar behaviour was reported by a number of workers previously in some oxidation reactions with cerium(IV) in different mineral acid media¹³. The reasons put forth by different authors to explain the behaviour include formation of inactive dimers or trimers from the active monomeric forms of cerium(IV) or formation of a stable cerium(IV) – substrate complex. The formation of such dimers or trimers, as it is, appears to be less probable at the concentrations of H_2SO_4 and Ce^{IV} employed in the present investigation. Even though the argument that active Ce^{IV} species may be bound in the form of stable cerium(IV)-substrate complex at progressively higher concentrations of Ce^{IV}

appears more convincing, we could not get any spectrophotometric evidence for the formation of such a complex.

Another pertinent point which deserves recognition is that the species $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2$ being neutral (w.r.t. charge) should have only a very limited solubility and hence very limited concentration in solution even if equilibria (A) and (B) dictate high concentration, depending upon $[\text{H}^+]$ and $[\text{HSO}_4^-]$. This being the situation, the individual molecules of $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2$ may interact physically forming small aggregates which are inactive and if there is excessive formation of $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2$ the smaller aggregates may become much bigger ones in size and may even precipitate out from solution. In other words, equilibrium (D) which was ignored upto now, plays a significant role in deciding $[\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2]$ in solution,

Our preliminary experiments showed that on addition of progressively larger amounts of NaHSO_4 in solution-form to solutions of $0.002 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ cerium(IV) perchlorate in 1.0 mol dm^{-3} HClO_4 , precipitation of yellow coloured mass took place at overall $[\text{HSO}_4^-]$ greater than $0.005 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. Analysis of the clear supernatant solution obtained in each case showed that the cerium(IV) concentration was much less than the expected, indicating removal of part of Ce^{IV} from the solution. From this hint, it may be argued that the concentration of the species $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2$ in solution can never exceed a certain maximum value, whatever may be the expected concentration in solution basing on equilibria (A) and (B), and equilibrium (D) may be acting as a vent for the removal of $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2$ -form from solution. Further, it may be that eventhough equilibria (A) to (C) are reversible, equilibrium (D) may not be so and in that case equilibrium (D) is only a vent but not a source of $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2$ -form of cerium(IV) species. In conclusion, the increase in initial $[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]$ does not contribute much to the effective increase in the concentration of $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2$ -form of the species in solution and hence there is a decrease in the rate constant with increase in the initial $[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]$.

Experimental

A 0.1 mol dm^{-3} solution of Te^{IV} was prepared afresh by dissolving sodium tellurite (L.R., B.D.H.) in double-distilled water and its strength verified⁴. A 0.1 mol dm^{-3} stock solutions of Ce^{IV} and Ce^{III} in 1.0 mol dm^{-3} sulfuric acid were prepared separately starting from ceric sulfate (99.9% pure, Indian Rare Earths Ltd.) and the cerium and acid contents of the solutions were also assessed². An approximately

4.0×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³ Ir^{III} solution in sulfuric acid was prepared starting from iridium(III) chloride (L.R., Loba) and diluted to the required volume with distilled water, after repeated evaporation with conc. sulfuric acid, to expel chloride, and the Ir^{III} content determined potentiometrically¹⁴. A ca. 8.0 mol dm⁻³ solution of LiClO₄ was prepared by neutralising Li₂CO₃ (G.P.R., B.D.H.) with 70% HClO₄ (G.R., Merck). All other chemicals used were of A.R. grade.

A Milton Roy Spectronic – 1201 UV – visible spectrophotometer with 1 cm path-length silica cells was used.

Procedure and kinetic measurements : All kinetic runs were carried out at a constant temperature of $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$ unless otherwise mentioned. Requisite amounts of all other reactants excepting cerium(IV) were equilibrated in the thermostat. The reaction was initiated by transferring a calculated amount of thermostated cerium(IV) into the reaction mixture. The course of the reaction was followed by measuring the absorbance of the aliquots drawn at different time intervals, at 400 nm. As no other species except cerium(IV) has any significant absorption at this wavelength, the absorbance of the solution was taken as a measure of the residual concentration of cerium(IV) at time 't'.

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